

Out of the Shadows: Revealing the Far-Reaching Impact of Dutch Dairy Production

Final report for bachelor Sustainable Innovation

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Abstract

The impact of Dutch dairy farming extends far beyond the Dutch borders. The vast majority of dairy fodder is produced elsewhere, with impacts in places that consumers do not know about. These are the ‘shadow places’ of Dutch dairy production. Although previous research has studied the overall environmental impacts of dairy, a localized understanding of the impacts related to fodder is lacking. This study examines the extent to which Dutch dairy farming is coupled to distant environments through fodder.

Through a combination of telecoupling and life cycle assessment, this study quantifies and localises environmental impacts in terms of eutrophication, ecotoxicity, land-, and water use. It shows that on average 60% of the impacts of a cow’s diet are localised in the shadow places. This study maps these impacts, revealing a complex web of 28 interconnected environments that constitute ‘Dutch’ dairy production. The findings show the ease with which this web changes, highlighting just how dynamic and interdependent dairy production is. It shows that local effects are the result of globally connected cause-effect relationships which cannot be studied in isolation.

This study underscores the reach of the effects of dairy farming in the Netherlands. It argues to use this as an advantage and discusses four mitigation strategies. Before any of these are implemented it is crucial to generate a deeper understanding of the complex interrelationships of the dairy production system. Only then can dairy’s burden on shadow places be reduced.

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1 Introduction

The environmental impacts of livestock production have garnered widespread public concern, particularly in the Netherlands where the "nitrogen crisis" is a widely recognized issue. With the Dutch livestock sector having grown too large, there is a pressing need for strict and impactful measures to reduce nitrogen emissions. However, the impact of livestock production extends far beyond the borders of the Netherlands, often unbeknownst to the public. It is crucial to understand these "outsourced" environmental impacts to effectively address the challenges caused by the Dutch livestock sector. A main contributor to these challenges is the Dutch dairy sector, in which several transformative changes have taken place over the years.

Over the past 100 years, milk output per cow has quadrupled. Although important, improved genetics are not the sole reason for such output growth. Proper nutrition and diet are crucial factors for a dairy cow to achieve its genetic production potential (Vandehaar & St-Pierre, 2006). Thanks to the shift from all-forage to supplemented forage diets, the current milk yield per cow is higher than it has ever been. Due to this shift, combined with globalization, the present-day diet of a Dutch dairy cow is not completely dependent on local land availability anymore. It can be said that a cow's diet has become decoupled from its surrounding land and local feed production capacities (Garrett et al., 2020). However, the diet is still bound to land, though not always as clearly and immediately visible as before. A part of the cow's diet, namely the fodder, is now being produced in the shadows, in other countries with effects neither visible to the farmer nor the consumer. This study aims to shed light upon these shadows by calculating and localising the environmental impacts bound to fodder production.

1.1 Problem exploration

In 2019, the Dutch cattle herd consisted of roughly 1,58 million dairy cows (CBS, 2023c). These cows each produce about 8900 kgs of milk every year (van der Meulen, 2022; ZuivelNL, 2020). With an average lifespan of 5,6 years and a productive lifespan of 3,41 years, each cow produces over 30.349 kgs of milk over their lifespan (CRV, 2021). To reach maximum productivity, an average lactating Dutch dairy cow consumes around 59kgs of feed, of which 53 kgs of forage and 6kgs of (compound) fodder per day (Eurofins Agro, 2011; Hospers et al., 2022). This means that, to feed the Dutch cattle herd for one day, over 93 million kgs of feed are required, ~9 million kgs of which are fodder. Furthermore, it is estimated that merely 7% of Dutch dairy cow fodder is produced in the Netherlands. Half of the remainder is imported from outside of Europe, which makes the Dutch dairy sector the primary consumer of non-EU fodder (Veraart et al., 2023). Evidently, great amounts of resources are required to feed the complete Dutch cattle herd, most of which are sourced elsewhere. And together with great amounts of resources come great amounts of impact.

There is plenty of research on the total environmental impacts of livestock production. One of the most cited works is the book by the Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO): "Livestock's long shadow", which describes the global environmental impact of livestock production (Steinfeld et al., 2006). The authors show that the global livestock sector has grown and intensified, whilst it has also decoupled output growth from land use. Nevertheless, feed crops used 33% of worldwide arable land in 2006. They also show that livestock production systems are spatially disconnected from their feed base and that livestock production competes actively with other sectors for land. Other relevant literature investigates the environmental impacts of European dairy/milk production by means of Life Cycle Assessments (LCA) (Baldini et al., 2017; Hospers et al., 2022; Thomassen et al., 2009; Yan et al., 2011). Some of these studies distinguish the impacts of cow feed in particular. But these are either outdated or focus solely on global warming potential (Hospers et al., 2022; Thomassen et al., 2009).

The essence of the reviewed literature is that there is a lot of information on the total environmental impacts per kg of milk and what part of this impact results from feed. However, the findings are outdated and the authors have not assigned locality to environmental impacts, meaning that they have not specified where the environmental impact occurs. For example, Hospers et al. (2022) calculated the carbon footprint (including land use change) per feed ingredient, but did neither localise impacts nor the origin of the feed ingredients.

Besides life cycle assessments, there are more theoretical approaches that study the sustainability of feed production. For example, a significant amount of telecoupling research has been conducted on soybean trade (da Silva et al., 2021; Gasparri & de Waroux, 2015; Silva et al., 2017; Sun et al., 2018; Torres et al., 2017). Telecoupling is a concept used to describe and understand the complex, interdependent relationships between coupled human and natural systems across distances and is most often used in multidisciplinary, qualitative studies on global supply chains. The research on soy demonstrates the complexity of global flows of fodder, and how its effects reach beyond the ex- and importing countries. Contrary to the LCA literature, the telecoupling research does pay close attention to the space dimension, but it most often does not quantify impacts. This leaves the question of how the diet of the Dutch dairy cow is linked to places beyond the Dutch borders, namely shadow places, unanswered. This is the research gap that this study intends to fill.

1.2 Research question

This study investigates where the feed ingredients originate from and what the corresponding local environmental impacts are. Both fodder and forage production scale and impacts are identified. The focus formally lays on fodder and forage is included for comparison, since forage is produced within the Netherlands and local impacts are already known. Once the impact of the cow's diet is localised, it becomes evident to what extent Dutch dairy production is telecoupled through global flows of fodder.

This will be achieved by answering the research question: *To what extent are Dutch dairy production and its environmental impacts telecoupled through fodder production?* This research question can be broken down into the following 3 sub-questions:

- 1) *What are the individual components of Dutch dairy cow fodder and where do they originate from?*
- 2) *What are the local environmental impacts of Dutch cow fodder production in terms of land use (change), water use, ecotoxicity, and eutrophication?*
- 3) *How are these environmental impacts proportionally divided over the shadow places?*

Answering this research question is valuable for three reasons. First, it brings a deeper understanding of the telecoupled Dutch dairy food system by highlighting spatially decoupled dependencies and impacts. Second, mapping is critical as identification, estimation, and localisation of impacts helps in evaluating sustainability trade-offs and is the key first step for designing effective interventions. Third, mapping impacts will generate more awareness of the widespread environmental impacts of dairy which can positively influence consumer choices.

2 Theoretical background

To enable the understanding of the connectedness of Dutch dairy production with the rest of the world through fodder production, two theoretical concepts are used. Firstly, the concept of shadow places is used to describe the problem and to highlight the importance of this research. Secondly, telecoupling is used as a heuristic device to further comprehend the case and to interpret the findings of this research. This chapter introduces these concepts and explains their contribution to this paper. Additionally, the value of using both of these concepts is greater than the sum of its parts. Both concepts fit well into each other, which this chapter illustrates.

2.1 Shadow places

Shadow places is a theoretical concept used to describe the forgotten physical areas that bear the burden of consumption (Plumwood, 2008). Therefore, it is of great use to illustrate the problem of the unknown environmental impacts of overseas fodder production for Dutch dairy cows. The value of this term goes beyond its metaphoric value of being able to “shed light” upon impacted areas that are invisible to the public.

Before being able to explain ‘shadow places’, it is important to start with a brief explanation of another term: dematerialisation. Dematerialisation describes the process of becoming more and more out of touch with the material conditions that support or enable our lives (Plumwood, 2008). The term ‘shadow places’ has been coined by Val Plumwood in 2008 to counter dematerialisation by questioning the capitalist exploitation, social injustice, and environmental issues related to the western consumption regime in a context of place. Shadow places are defined as “all of those places that produce or are affected by the commodities that you consume, places consumers don’t know about, don’t want to know about, and in a commodity regime don’t ever need to know about or take responsibility for” (Plumwood, 2008, p. 146). Plumwood argues that it is important to not only care for *your* ‘place of dwelling’, but to also take responsibility for those places that ‘build’ *you*. She encourages society and academics to recognize that places of production are places that support and grow *you* and that *you* should take care of those as well.

It now becomes clear why shadow places fit perfectly in the description of the Dutch dairy production case. The nitrogen crisis has brought immense attention to the environmental impacts of livestock production (including dairy) within Dutch borders. However, the attention to local impacts often overshadows the places that enable the Dutch livestock production system to begin with. Following the argumentation of Plumwood, the shadow places of dairy fodder should be treated with the same level of care and attention as the places and nature within the Netherlands, our place of dwelling. The first step in doing so is locating these shadow places and quantifying and allocating the environmental impacts of fodder production.

The concept of shadow places eloquently highlights the importance of research that focuses on the localisation of impacts. Besides justifying this research, shadow places is used to recognize the phenomena of invisible impacts in invisible places and to argue for a future system which is built upon responsibility and care for the places that are affected by feed production. But, to enable a deeper understanding of how the Netherlands is connected to these shadow places, a description of the case through the lens of shadow places does not suffice. The theoretical concept of telecoupling complements the concept of shadow places by adding more nuance to the underlying dynamics that connect places of dwelling and shadow places.

2.2 Telecoupling

The field of telecoupling suggests that studying sustainability in an isolated place does not suffice in a globalized world. According to Kapsar et al. (2019), the human-environment interactions between different geographical locations have profound implications for sustainability research and management. This is also true for geographically decoupled fodder production-consumption systems. Hence, this paper uses the relatively new concept of telecoupling (2013) to frame and reflect on the sustainability impacts on the shadow places of fodder production. The academic field of telecoupling is still taking shape, and thanks to its novelty and interdisciplinary usefulness there is a lot of flexibility in how it is applied. Hence, according to Kapsar et al. (2019), there are three ways in which telecoupling is applied in the academic literature. Namely, as a framework, a concept, and a phenomenon. The first two, most prominent, ways are discussed below in order to clarify how telecoupling is used in this research.

Telecoupling was invented as an integrated framework to systematically describe socioeconomic and environmental interactions among coupled human and natural systems (CHANS). Telecouplings consist of five components: systems, agents, flows, causes, and effects. To identify and understand interactions in and between systems, the framework distinguishes sending, receiving, and spillover systems and their socioeconomic and environmental components (agents, causes and effects). The connections between these systems are called flows and can be both physical (material, organisms) and non-physical (information, capital) (Liu et al., 2013). For example, in the case of Dutch dairy fodder, shadow places can be seen as sending systems, the Netherlands as the receiving system, and spillover systems could be downstream areas affected by water pollution or scarcity. An effect in the Netherlands is that less land is allocated to fodder production, freeing up land for other industries and systems, which further emphasizes the telecoupled nature of the case. The other side of this effect is the increased land use (change) and other sustainability impacts in shadow places, reducing the possibilities for alternative land use purposes.

The telecoupling framework is frequently used in the field of research on fodder production, specifically on Brazilian soy (da Silva et al., 2021; Gasparri & de Waroux, 2015; Silva et al., 2017; Torres et al., 2017). These papers aim to holistically describe the CHANS of soy production, which is achieved by applying the telecoupling framework. The authors analyse every telecoupling component to understand the causes, relevant actor roles, and affected areas of the Brazilian soybean trade. For example, Silva et al. (2017) use telecoupling to show that the growth of the Sino-Brazilian soy trade has cascading effects on Brazilian maize cultivation, prices, and exports. Different authors apply the telecoupling framework to assist in explaining the (historical) system dynamics (Silva et al., 2017; Torres et al., 2017), or to assess (future) policy interventions (Gasparri & de Waroux, 2015; Torres et al., 2017). From the aforementioned literature, only da Silva et al. (2021) quantify effects by using additional modelling approaches. This demonstrates that telecoupling alone is often not enough to quantify effects and additional, complementary methods are used to do so.

Hence, an identified limitation of the telecoupling framework is that the current research is often only descriptive. The vast majority of telecoupling research describes processes qualitatively, but lack quantitative analyses on the effects that telecouplings have on a local level. Besides quantifying effects, proving the causality of the effects has also been identified as a limitation of the telecoupling framework (Carlson et al., 2018). These limitations also apply to the papers by Silva et al., Torres et al., and Gasparri and de Waroux.

A different way telecoupling is used, according to Kapsar (2019), is as a concept. Here, specific telecoupling components are identified as affected by a telecoupling process but the framework as such is not applied (Kapsar et al., 2019). Some terminology is used but not to the point of active identification and investigation of all the components of the telecoupled process. That the researched case can be conceptualised as a telecoupling is a given in these papers and the language of telecoupling is used to further describe the case. Often, the aim of such research is to investigate the sustainability implications of the telecoupling in the studied case. Such research often has a multi-disciplinary approach, which expands on the capabilities of the telecoupling framework to better understand and explain certain telecoupled system characteristics (Schierhorn et al., 2016; Veraart et al., 2020). The study by Sun et al. (2018) is another excellent example of research in which telecoupling is used as a concept. In this study, the authors analyse the environmental effects of soybean trade by looking at the per-hectare nitrogen balance. They show that due to soy's natural ability to fix nitrogen, cultivating soy can actually reduce nitrogen in soil and water that would otherwise result from additional nitrogen fertiliser. They conclude that the receiving countries that import soy also suffer negative environmental effects, as arable land is used to cultivate different crops, which causes a significant nitrogen spillover into the environment (Sun et al., 2018).

The way telecoupling is used mainly depends on the aim of the research. Whilst research with the aim of holistically describing a CHANS uses telecoupling as a framework, research that focuses on (quantifying) sustainability implications of a certain telecoupling uses it as a concept. The aim of this study aligns with that of research that uses telecoupling as a concept, which is examining the environmental effects of telecoupled dairy fodder production in shadow places. Similar to research that uses telecoupling as a concept, not all components of the telecoupling framework are important to the aim of this study. Primarily systems, flows, and effects are of interest to answer the research question.

Therefore, it is concluded that applying telecoupling through the rigid boundaries of a framework is irrelevant to answer the research question, and a thorough qualitative description of the CHANS of Dutch fodder does not provide the insights that lay within the scope of this study. Whilst shadow places describe and highlight the importance of the problem and envision the desired situation, telecoupling functions as a lens through which the case of spatially divided fodder production and consumption is explained. It is used to describe how the shadow places of production are connected to the Netherlands through fodder flow and to describe what the impacts of this flow are. Additionally, telecoupling serves as an interpretative frame through which the results of this study are discussed.

3 Methodology

Telecoupled production systems, such as dairy fodder production, require a holistic approach to quantify and spatially allocate its environmental effects. Since one of the limitations of a telecoupling analysis is that it often lacks quantification, and since an LCA aims at this, this paper employs an LCA-inspired methodology. In return, telecoupling is used to explain and interpret the localisation of effects, something that is normally not done in an LCA. Using LCA in a telecoupling context has been done effectively before (Henriksson et al., 2018; Lu et al., 2022). Furthermore, Parra Paitan and Verburg (2019) extensively reviewed a wide variety of methods for assessing the impacts of telecoupled agricultural production, concluding that an LCA is an attractive, flexible tool provided that it is made spatially explicit (Parra Paitan & Verburg, 2019). A clarification on how this spatial dimension is guaranteed is given in this chapter. But first, to explain the methods used to operationalise the research question, a brief introduction to regular LCA methodology is given.

3.1 Introduction to regular Life Cycle Assessment

According to the ISO standards 14040 and 14044, an LCA consists of four general phases. First comes the goal and scope definition phase, during which the aim, system boundaries, functional unit and limitations of the study are defined. A life cycle inventory (LCI) constitutes the second phase. During this phase, an inventory of flows from and to the ecosphere is determined for every life stage. In the third phase, a life cycle impact assessment is made (LCIA). An LCIA aims to evaluate the potential impacts on the environment and human health resulting from the flows determined in the LCI phase. The final and fourth phase is the interpretation phase during which the results are summarized, conclusions are discussed, and recommendations are given. Even though there seems to be an order in these phases, the phases depend on each other and should be reviewed carefully over the full duration of the study. None of the phases should be considered completed before the full study is finished (ISO, 1997, 2006). However, a full LCA according to ISO standards is not required nor enough on its own to answer the research question of this study. Only the desired parts of a LCA are taken for the LCA-inspired methodology which is supported by the theoretical concepts discussed in the previous chapter.

3.2 Goal and scope definition

The goal of this study is to find out to what extent Dutch dairy production is telecoupled through its fodder production. The production system that this study is interested in is the fodder production system, from farm to farm gate. Processes such as milling, grinding and pressing (to obtain e.g. soybean meal or palm kernel expeller) are formally included in this study since the selected database on environmental impacts also includes this. Transportation to possible processing facilities is not taken into account. Likewise, transportation to the Netherlands, processing (mixing and bagging of the raw ingredients) as well as end-of-life phase are excluded from this research. These are excluded since it is expected that the main environmental impacts of these phases are either not the impacts that lay within the scope of this study (non-local impacts such as CO₂) or already have been studied extensively (end-of-life).

Figure 1: Life Cycle Assessment of fodder production system boundaries

The diet of a cow consists mainly of forage which is supplemented by fodder. Forage is produced on and around the farm (fresh grass and silage), whilst the ingredients of fodder are produced all over the world. Furthermore, the amount of fodder a cow eats before lactating is only 5,8% of its total fodder consumption according to one study (Hospers et al., 2022). Other studies do not clarify this distinction but instead only mention the fodder intake of lactating dairy cows. Hence, only the amount of fodder that is required for an average Dutch dairy cow over its productive lifetime, which is 3,41 years (CRV, 2021), is taken into account. The functional unit (FU) is defined as the amount of fodder [kg] required to produce 1 kg of milk and is achieved by dividing the productive lifetime fodder consumption by the lifetime production of a cow, which was 30349 kg in 2019 (van der Meulen, 2022). The chosen FU makes it possible to adjust the results to any scale by simple multiplication, whilst also fitting within the context of similar LCA studies.

Besides forage and fodder, wet by-products also make up a considerable amount (5,8%) of a dairy cow's diet (Hospers et al., 2022). Nevertheless, since these are (recycled) by-products from the Dutch food industry they lay outside the scope of this research. Furthermore, organically fed cows are not taken into account as these make up only a small percentage of the cow population in the Netherlands (2,4% (CBS, 2023a)), and a larger portion of their diet is produced locally (van Wagenberg et al., 2017). It is also acknowledged that male cows are an unavoidable part of the cow stock on dairy farms, yet their fodder requirements are excluded to prevent double counting and allocation problems with beef production. Likewise, the meat from the dairy cow is considered a by-product, laying outside of the scope of this study. Therefore, all the fodder consumed by the cow is linked to its dairy production.

3.3 Lifecycle inventory analysis

Based on the goal and scope definition this research employs an adjusted version of an LCI. Even though the exact composition of fodder is considered an industry secret, two studies make an estimation (Hospers et al., 2022; Veraart et al., 2023). They do this by analysing the market and using prices and nutritional requirements to estimate the fodder formula. Because there are considerable differences between the estimations of both sources, an average is deliberately not chosen to cope with these differences. Instead, the estimation in the study by Veraart et al. is chosen for the main line of results whilst the other is discussed as part of the sensitivity analysis. Equal practice is in place for the varied fodder intake data (Hospers et al., 2022; van der Meulen, 2022; Veraart et al., 2023), where Veraart et al. is also taken as the main line of results. Besides quantities, the origin of each ingredient is also required in order to localise impacts. This goes beyond a traditional LCI and secures the spatial dimension of the study.

Since it is not possible to physically track the origin of each ingredient, the origin of each fodder ingredient is calculated by determining the market mix per ingredient in the Netherlands. This is done in the report “Herkomst Diervoedergrondstoffen”, but the origins are categorized as “Dutch, Europe, and outside of Europe” (Veraart et al., 2023). Such categorization is too broad to answer the research question, which is why a trade balance is set up per ingredient for the year 2019. With the help of Eurostat trade data (Eurostat, 2022) and Dutch domestic production data from Statistics Netherlands (CBS, 2023b), every country’s share in the Dutch market mix is calculated.

$$\text{share of country } X = \frac{(\text{import} - \text{export})_{\text{country } X}}{(\text{Dutch production} + \text{import} - \text{export})_{\text{all countries}}}$$

Then the data is manipulated to achieve a list which only includes countries with a net import share larger than 1%, the remaining countries are grouped as “other countries”. Soybean meal and hulls are a special case, since Dutch soy production is virtually zero, yet according to the trade balance it net exports processed soy products. To properly localize the impact of soy the market mix of soy is used rather than those of the processed soy products. Other fodder ingredient-specific assumptions are discussed in appendix A.

3.4 Localised lifecycle impact analysis

Subsequently, the localised impact of fodder production is calculated. This requires the integration of parts from the LCI (flows from the ecosphere, e.g. water and flows to the ecosphere, e.g. fertilizer) and LCIA (assessment of the impact of these flows). This study focuses on environmental impacts that have local effects. Emissions into the air, such as carbon dioxide, are excluded from this study. These environmental impacts have global effects and have already been calculated in previous research (Hospers et al., 2022), and are therefore not relevant to achieving the aim of this study. The environmental impacts that are included in the analysis are Land use [pt.], Land use change [kg CO₂ eq.], water use [m³ deprived], ecotoxicity water [CTUe], and freshwater- and terrestrial eutrophication [kg P eq.] and [mol N eq.].

In the calculation of water use, the Available WATER REMaining (AWARE) indicator is used. AWARE calculates the amount of water remaining after the needs of humans and ecosystems are met, and is an area-specific indicator of water scarcity (Boulay et al., 2018). Land use is assessed based on points [pt.] rather than [m²] to capture more than just land occupation. For that matter, land use is calculated through the spatially-explicit LANCA model (De Laurentiis et al., 2018), which uses soil quality as an indicator for the environmental impacts of using land for a certain purpose. It is expressed in the dimensionless unit of points [pt.], which is the result of the weighing and aggregation of 4 soil quality indicators (erosion resistance, groundwater regeneration, water infiltration and biotic production). It covers both land occupation and land transformation impacts and is therefore an adequate representation of the land use impact of fodder production.

Additionally, land use change is included as it is an easier-to-interpret indicator that represents deforestation. Terrestrial eutrophication relates to the excessive inputs of nutrients, mainly nitrogen and phosphorus and their impacts on land-based ecosystems. Freshwater eutrophication, on the other hand, considers the consequences of the nutrient run-off into freshwater ecosystems and the impacts of freshwater eutrophication involve algal blooms, fish kills and the general disruption of ecological balance. Similarly, ecotoxicity of water also relates to the health of aquatic ecosystems. But, instead of excessive nutrients, the environmental damage is mainly caused by the use of pesticides and other chemicals during agricultural production. It is expressed in Comparative Toxic Unit ecosystem (CTUe) and simplified it means that more CTUe results in more damage to the ecosystem, in terms of decreased biodiversity and decreased species population.

According to Parra Paitan and Verburg (2019), it is important to use place-specific emission and weighting factors where possible. This means that, for example, a kg of soy produced in Brazil can have a different environmental impact compared to a kg of soy produced in Argentina or in the United States. They acknowledge that this can be difficult for large-scale spatially-explicit analysis, such as this study, due to the lack of place-specific data (Parra Paitan & Verburg, 2019). However, this study attempts to account for place-specific emission factors on a country scale as much as data availability allows.

In order to complete the LCI and LCIA steps, various methodologies were explored. First, the eco-costs methodology and dataset looked promising due to its data availability, accessibility and the use of place-specific factors. But, after deeper exploration a mistake was found in the dataset, which was later confirmed by the founder of the methodology (J. Vogtländer, personal communication, June 6, 2023). Hence, the Agri-footprint 6.3 (Blonk, 2022) and Ecoinvent 3.9.1 (Ecoinvent, 2022) LCI databases are chosen, complemented by the Environmental Footprint LCIA method (European Commission, 2023). These databases use the economic allocation principle to calculate the environmental impacts of certain “by-products” of crops, e.g. soybean hulls or sugar beet molasses. This means that the impacts of a crop are divided over its co-products based on their economic contribution, and ensures that these impacts are fairly distributed. Despite the fact that these databases are widely recognized and used in the vast majority of LCA research, some limitations in the context of this study are present and discussed in the adequate subchapter.

Finally, the findings are visualised and mapped in a manner that shows how the environmental impacts are spatially divided over the shadow places, which answers the third sub-question. The theoretical concepts of shadow places and telecoupling are used to interpret these findings and answer the research question.

3.5 Limitations

Parra Paitan and Verburg (2019) discuss the limitations of applying LCA to telecoupled supply chains, such as missing significant impacts due to the exclusion of certain inputs, outputs or entire life stages, as well as the arbitrary selection of impact indicators. These limitations are particularly concerning in comparative LCAs, since excluding certain life stages or impacts could determine the conclusion in such LCA studies. Although this study is not a comparative LCA, one must still be cautious when interpreting the results of this research. Furthermore, the authors also state that feedbacks and spillover effects are often not taken into account in an LCA (Parra Paitan & Verburg, 2019). This limitation is acknowledged here, yet not resolved as the scope of this study excludes cause-effect relationships. Like many other LCAs, linearity of effects is assumed in this study, which also results in the exclusion of feedbacks. To explore governance options in dairy cow fodder production systems, a methodology with forecasting capabilities that includes feedbacks and spillover effects is recommended.

Standardized functional units (FUs), such as Fat and Protein Corrected Milk (FPCM), have been suggested for dairy lifecycle assessments to enable better comparisons between studies (Baldini et al., 2017; Yan et al., 2011). This research uses a different FU, since less data is available on the average fat and protein percentages of Dutch milk, but it is easily converted to FPCM for comparison. Other concerns mentioned by the authors include site specificity of impacts, calls for explicit system boundaries, the required broad range of impact categories, and the need for sensitivity analysis, which are all dealt with appropriately in this study. However, social and economic sustainability indicators are excluded in this study, which risks losing insight into the sustainability dynamics of telecoupled fodder production systems (Parra Paitan & Verburg, 2019). These components of sustainability are consciously placed outside of scope since the order of causality between farming crops and e.g. poverty is harder to quantitatively prove than between crops and environmental impacts.

The primary limitation of the used LCA methodologies is the way land use is represented. Whilst it is a robust model of impacts on different soil qualities and functions, which incorporates the impacts of land occupation, it does not provide a complete view of the environmental impact of land use. Even though soil quality is related to biodiversity, it is not the best representation of biodiversity loss (Mattila et al., 2011). LCA is generally limited in representing land use because of the complexity and broadness of land use. A framework or method that assesses land use on soil quality, occupation, greenhouse gas (GHG) balance and biodiversity comprehensively yet not too complex has not been found yet (Mattila et al., 2011). Besides, the complexity of the LANCA model and the dimensionless unit [pt.] make it difficult to interpret.

To mitigate these limitations, this study employs a second methodology for calculating land use as part of the sensitivity analysis. A land occupation method is used to represent the costs of allocating land to agriculture, rather than it fulfilling its ecological potential by being allocated to nature. Land occupation is calculated by using country specific yield data (FAO, 2023), and multiplying this by a biodiversity factor. The biodiversity factor is based upon the world biodiversity map of vascular plants (Barthlott et al., 1996) and relative to the biodiversity density in the Netherlands. This results in an easier to interpret, yet similarly spatially explicit indicator for land use [m² Dutch land eq.]. However, the biodiversity factor is fairly arbitrary and has limited boundaries as to what impacts or kind of biodiversity are included. Additionally, this study also includes land use change to incorporate the GHG-balance aspect of land use. Even though CO₂ emissions are a global impact, it represents the local problem of deforestation, which is why it is included in this study. This study attempts to include all aspects of land use through this triad of methods.

Furthermore, the market mix approach, also applied in Veraart et al. (2023) to find ingredients' countries of origin has two unavoidable caveats. First, using this approach shows nothing more than the average origin of a bag of a certain fodder ingredient that is present in the Netherlands, and does not take the use purpose into account. This could technically mean that even though 50% of e.g. sunflower meal in the Netherlands comes from Argentina, the dairy fodder industry only buys sunflower meal from Ukraine. Due to the fact that it is not possible to physically track the origin or purpose of the ingredients, the resulting uncertainty simply needs to be accepted.

Second, this approach falls short on crops that are traded through certain countries, or grown in one and then processed in another. For example, soy may be grown in Brazil and then exported to Belgium. Belgium then exports a part of their imported soy to the Netherlands. The trade balance now suggests that soy is produced in Belgium whilst the impacts lay in Brazil. Similar problems occur for processed products. To mitigate this limitation common sense is used to manually adjust obvious outliers (e.g. soy in Belgium or palm kernel expeller in Germany), but non-obvious cases are missed through this mitigation strategy and remain an uncertainty. This is not only a problem in this study and it commonly appears in LCA databases or the study by Veraart et al. (2023).

Besides LCA, other quantification models are available and have been considered. Partial equilibrium models, such as the MEAT model (Burke et al., 2009; Galloway et al., 2007). This (economic) model estimates land, water, and nitrogen inputs to feed and meat production. It uses the concept of embedded (physically present) and virtual (required for production but lost to the environment) inputs to calculate and make spatially explicit the resource use and transfer among countries. The model sheds light upon previously hidden costs, in terms of resources, of traded livestock products (Burke et al., 2009). The model has heavier data requirements and adjustments to the model would be needed to better fit the research question. Yet the results would likely be similar to the current methods, which is showing the hidden costs of fodder production, and therefore the MEAT model is not the preferred methodology.

4 Results

This chapter is split into 4 sections. The first three each give the numerical answer to one of the three aforementioned sub-questions: 1) What are the individual components of Dutch dairy cow fodder and where do they originate from? 2) What are the local environmental impacts of Dutch cow fodder production in terms of land use (change), water use, ecotoxicity, and eutrophication? And 3) How are these environmental impacts proportionally divided over the shadow places? Afterwards, through a sensitivity analysis, alternative assumptions and their effects on the results are discussed.

4.1 The individual components of Dutch dairy cow fodder and their origins

In order to answer the research question “To what extent are Dutch dairy production and its environmental impacts telecoupled through its fodder production?” it is first necessary to identify the individual components (and their origins) of Dutch dairy cow fodder.

In 2019, the complete herd of Dutch dairy cows, which are 1.577.964 cows (CBS, 2023c), ate 3.201.851 tonnes of fodder (Veraart et al., 2023). This comes down to a productive lifetime average of 2029,1 kgs/year per cow or 6919 kgs during its productive lifetime of 3,41 years. In terms of the functional unit, this means that ~0,228 kgs of fodder are required per kg of milk.

In Veraart et al. (2023) the composition of both low and high-protein fodder is given, however, without clarification of the respective ratios. According to Hospers et al., the ratio between low-protein and high-protein fodder is 58% to 42%. This ratio is used to fill the data gap in Veraart et al.’s (2023) work and figure 2 shows the resulting composition of both fodders condensed into one. About 50% of the fodder consists of protein-rich co-products from oil crops (palm kernel expeller, soybean hulls, and soybean-, sunflower- and rapeseed meal). About 32% of the fodder composition comprises non-processed cereals, which are also consumable by humans. The “other” category consists of ingredients with a contribution smaller than 1% and is merely represented in the graph to give a complete view of the fodder composition but lays outside the scope of this study.

Figure 2: Percentual composition of Dutch dairy fodder in 2019 according to Veraart et al. (2023). The category *Other* consists of beet pulp, chalk, magnesium oxide, palm oil, premix, salt, peas, wheat, wheat gluten feed, and other minor additions

Figure 3 shows a world map of the aggregate origin of fodder in 2019. It is calculated by combining the data from figure 2 with the market mix per ingredient, which is shown in appendix B. Only 7% of the total dairy fodder is produced in the Netherlands, whilst geographical Europe produces just over 44% and the rest of the world is responsible for 43%. This division is a near-perfect equivalence to the estimation of origins in Veraart et al. (2023), which further validates these results. A bit less than 1% is produced by “other countries” which is a conglomeration of countries which had a market share smaller than 1% per ingredient. The remainder of the weight consists of “other ingredients”.

Figure 3 shows that Ukraine and Germany are the largest European producers of fodder with a contribution of respectively 20% and 12%. The Netherlands mainly imports maize, rapeseed and sunflower products from Ukraine, and the majority of the other cereals are sourced from Germany. Indonesia, Brazil and the USA are the largest producers of fodder outside of Europe (12%, 11%, and 9% respectively), which predominantly produce high-protein fodder ingredients.

Figures 2 and 3, together with the market mix per ingredient, visualise the answer to the first sub-question “*What are the individual components of Dutch dairy fodder and where do they originate from?*”.

Figure 3: Aggregate origin of Dutch dairy fodder in 2019

4.2 The local environmental impacts of fodder production

The next step in this research is to find the local environmental impacts of fodder production in terms of land use (change), water use, eutrophication and ecotoxicity. Figure 4 presents these indicators in terms of the contribution an ingredient makes to the total of the corresponding impact indicator. Figure 4 is complemented by the absolute values per ingredient in appendix C and full tables can be found in the complementary data files.

Looking at the differences between weight- and impact contribution can give more insights into which ingredients contribute disproportionately relative to their weight (= first blue bar in figure 4). Soybean meal is the prime example of this since all the environmental impacts are higher than the ingredient's weight share. However, these differences must be interpreted with care. First of all, it is important to note that while some ingredients may disproportionately pollute, they may also disproportionately contribute to dairy cow's diet (e.g. a kg of high-protein content cannot be substituted by a kg of grass). On top of this, for processed ingredients (e.g. beet molasses), the co-product's economic value is often higher than its weight share. For example, a kg of sugar beet may produce only 40 grams of molasses, yet the economic value share among the other sugar beet coproducts may be 10%. This, in combination with the realisation that 5 kgs of raw product may be required to produce 1 kg of processed product (which is a low mass allocation share), comprise the explanation for most of these differences. These nuances must be taken into account whilst interpreting the results.

Nevertheless, some notable results from table one are that cereal crops (e.g. maize, rye and triticale) contribute to most of the ecotoxicity of water. Zooming in on maize shows that maize amply generates the highest water deprivation, which means that maize production requires a lot of water in countries with high water demand (by humans and ecosystems) and relatively small water availability. Moreover, soybean meal clearly has the highest land use (change) impact, which is the result of the infamous deforestation of the Amazon forest. On the contrary, whilst the expansion of palm plantations is the main driver of deforestation in Indonesia, the environmental impact of palm kernel expeller is relatively low. A possible explanation could be a low economic allocation share together with a high mass allocation share. A similar explanation is expected to hold for citrus pulp.

Additionally, figure 4 also shows relatively high values for terrestrial eutrophication (14,1% for soybean meal compared to an 11% weight share). These values do not correspond with the fact that soybeans have a negative nitrogen balance (Sun et al., 2018). A possible explanation for this disparity is that the empirical base for the nitrogen balance calculation is based in China (Sun et al., 2018), not in the United States or Brazil from where the Netherlands imports its soy. A conclusion may be that soy production in these countries uses nitrogen fertilizer to achieve higher yields or in combination with other fertilizers, despite it not being necessary.

Figure 4: Environmental impacts of dairy fodder in 2019, as a percentage of total per impact indicator. *QTY* = kgs of fodder per functional unit, *EUT-FW* = freshwater eutrophication, *EUT-TR* = terrestrial eutrophication, *WU* = localised water use in terms of m³ deprived, *TOX-W* = freshwater ecotoxicity, *LUC* = land use change, *LU-S* = land use based on soil quality

Although insightful, looking at every ingredient’s contribution to the total impact does not completely answer the sub-question. The absolute values make up the core of the answer, but they unfortunately are not as easily interpreted as percentages. Hence, the totals per indicator for the FU are compared to the environmental impacts forage has in the Netherlands in table 1. This gives an idea of just how much shadow places are affected compared to impacts visible on Dutch land.

According to Hospers et al. (2022), the forage share (~85%) of a Dutch dairy cow’s diet is made up of a combination of fresh grass, and grass- and maize silage, and is assumed to be 100% domestically produced. Note that per 1 kg of milk, about ten times less fodder is fed compared to forage, yet the implications on shadow places are similar, if not bigger. Table 1 shows that fodder has a larger share in terms of water use (85%), freshwater ecotoxicity (81,2%) and land use change (100%). And because a small percentage of fodder is produced in the Netherlands, table 1 also shows the share of “imported” feed and impacts to give an idea of what share of the diet is located in the shadow places.

In this study, all results are given per FU: fodder required to produce 1 kg of milk. But because the research question refers to “Dutch dairy production” it makes sense to scale the results to the complete (non-organic) dairy production of the Netherlands. This was ~13,7 billion kgs of milk in 2019 (CBS, 2023c; van der Meulen, 2022), which requires a total of 3,12 billion kgs of fodder. Table 1 also displays the total impacts of the total Dutch dairy production in 2019. This yields a shocking display of just how much environmental impact Dutch dairy production really has through its fodder, most of which is located in shadow places. For example, the amount of CO₂ eq. released due to LUC is equal to ~10 billion car-driven kilometres (CLO, 2019).

	QTY [kg]	EUT-FW [kg P eq.]	EUT-TR [mol N eq.]	LU-S [pt.]	WU [m ³ depr. eq.]	TOX-W [CTUe]	LUC [kg CO ₂ eq.]
Total forage	2,02458	6,62E-05	0,017329	27,44895	0,010749	7,745237	2,4E-05
Total fodder	0,227989	6,01E-05	0,003969	22,08265	0,062897	33,46712	0,079667
Fodder share of feed	10,1%	47,6%	18,6%	44,6%	85,4%	81,2%	100,0%
Share imported	9,4%	42,4%	16,2%	43,3%	85,2%	79,9%	100,0%
Total fodder NL/year	3,12E+9	0,82E+6	54,39E+6	3,027E+11	0,86E+9	4,58E+11	1,09E+9

Table 1: Comparison between environmental impacts of fodder (93% shadow places) and forage (100% domestic production), according to forage intake and composition from Hospers et al. (2022). QTY = kgs of fodder per functional unit, EUT-FW = freshwater eutrophication, EUT-TR = terrestrial eutrophication, WU = localised water use in terms of m³ deprived, TOX-W = freshwater ecotoxicity, LUC = land use change, LU-S = land use based on soil quality

4.3 Proportional division of environmental impacts per country

The final sub-question that needs to be answered to enable answering the research question is: “How are these environmental impacts proportionally divided over the shadow places?”. This is done by creating six global impact maps. Figures 5-10 visualise how each impact indicator is proportionally divided over the Netherlands and the shadow places. In-depth numerical values, as well as larger, interactive versions of the maps, can be found in the complementary data files.

The results reveal that most of the environmental impacts of fodder production are concentrated in a few countries, namely: Brazil, the United States, Ukraine, and Germany. The most outstanding country on 5 out of 6 maps (excluding water use) is Brazil. The results show that Brazil bears considerable impacts in most categories. Land use and land use change stand out the most, in which Brazil’s contribution is 25% and 72% respectively. Next to Brazil, figures 5 and 8 show that Ukrainian soil is significantly affected by fodder production. Moreover, Ukraine also stands out in terms of water deprivation caused by fodder production (50% of the total water use), followed by the United States with 35% in the same category. The maps also show that the production of fodder crops in Germany comes with excessive nutrient flows resulting from fertilizer use (figure 5 and 6), and disproportionate damage to soil and water ecosystems (figures 8 and 10).

It is once again tempting to compare the impact share with the weight share in figure 3. Although here the impact and weight shares are distributed per country instead of per ingredient, one must still be careful when making these comparisons. The same, previously mentioned nuances apply in and between these maps as in figure 4.

Besides the largest affected countries, these maps shed light upon all the other shadow places of Dutch dairy production and therewith answer the third sub-question. Before all the showcased results can be synthesized into an answer to the research question a sensitivity analysis is performed to examine the effects of alternative assumptions.

Spatial distribution of terrestrial eutrophication

Terrestrial Eutrophication share 0,01% 27,26%

Figure 5: Spatial distribution of terrestrial eutrophication caused by Dutch dairy fodder in 2019

Spatial distribution of freshwater eutrophication

Freshwater Eutrophication share 0,00% 31,24%

Figure 6: Spatial distribution of freshwater eutrophication caused by Dutch dairy fodder in 2019

Spatial distribution of water use

Water use share 0,00% 50,26%

Figure 7: Spatial distribution of water use impacts caused by Dutch dairy fodder in 2019

Spatial distribution of ecotoxicity of water

Ecotoxicity water share 0,00% 33,79%

Figure 8: Spatial distribution of water ecotoxicity impacts caused by Dutch dairy fodder in 2019

Spatial distribution of land use change

Land use change share 0,00% 72,53%

Figure 9: Spatial distribution of land use change caused by Dutch dairy fodder in 2019

Spatial distribution of land use

Land use share 0,00% 25,48%

Figure 10: Spatial distribution of land use impacts caused by Dutch dairy fodder in 2019

4.4 Sensitivity analysis

4.4.1 Fodder required per FU

There is a direct linear relationship between the environmental impacts per FU and the amount of fodder [kg] that is required per FU (1 kg of milk). Therefore, it is of interest to see in what range the amount of fodder per functional unit may lay. Table 2 presents the matrix of assumptions on lifetime milk production (vertical) and productive lifetime fodder consumption per cow (horizontal). The combination that yields 100% in the table is the combination of assumptions used in the results. Table 2 shows that the amount of fodder per FU, thus all the absolute environmental impact values per FU could be between 15% lower or 23% higher than the current results.

Fodder/FU	Fodder consumption productive lifetime[kg]	(Veraart et al., 2023) 1	(Veraart et al., 2023) 2	(Hospers et al., 2022)	(van der Meulen, 2022)
Lifetime milk production [kg]		6145 kg	6919 kg	7033 kg	8525 kg
(van der Meulen, 2022)	30349 kg	89%	100%	102%	123%
(Hoogeveen, 2022)	30607 kg	88%	99%	101%	122%
(CRV, 2021)	31553 kg	85%	96%	98%	119%

Table 2: Sensitivity analysis on the amount of fodder required per FU.

4.4.2 Alternative land use methodology

As section 3.5 discusses, this study employs an additional alternative methodology for calculating land use impact. This methodology is based on crop yield data, which is weighted by a biodiversity factor. It results in both a wider coverage of all the aspects of land use in LCA and a more tangible impact indicator.

Similar to figure 10, figure 11 maps the distribution of land use by the alternative method. The precise eye could distinguish the two based on the contribution difference of Indonesia. In the land use calculation through the LANCA model Indonesia has a share of 13%, and through the alternative method this is merely 1%. This can be explained by the relatively low land coverage that is needed to produce 1 kg of palm kernel expeller in combination with a low economic allocation factor. The 12% reduction is broadly distributed over other countries with smaller shares. The fact that there are very small differences in terms of proportional distribution between the two methods confirms the validity of the alternative method.

The analysis shows that 0,46 m² of Dutch land equivalent is needed for fodder production related to 1 kg of produced milk. The area used for forage in the Netherlands is 1,1 million hectares, or 0,8 m² per FU (ZuivelNL, 2020). This shows that an additional 58% of land elsewhere is needed for the production of fodder, excluding wet-by products. This study's total of 1,26 is only 0,02 m² off compared to a total of 1,28 m² needed per kg of milk (Thomassen et al., 2009), and within the 25-75 percentile range shown in the study by Baldini et al. (2017). However, it is assumed that these studies did not correct for biodiversity as they did not mention it. Contrarily, the total of 1,26 m² is relatively low compared to the global average of 8,6 m² per kg of milk according to Poore and Nemecek (2018). This disparity puts the validity of the alternative method in doubt.

Spatial distribution of land use by alternative method

Figure 11: Alternative spatial distribution of land use impacts (through yield data, weighted by relative biodiversity compared to NL) caused by Dutch dairy fodder in 2019

4.4.3 Alternative fodder composition

An alternative to the fodder composition data from Veraart et al. (2023) is the fodder composition data used in the study by Hospers et al. (2022), which is visualised in figure 12. The main differences between the two are the large share of wheat products (15% compared to >1%), the larger share of palm kernel expeller (17% compared to 12%), as well as the 1:1 substitution of soybean meal by soybean hulls. In turn, it has no rye, triticale, beet molasses, or citrus pulp. Consequently, these dissimilarities in fodder composition produce a different aggregate origin map (complementary data).

First of all, France took Germany's place in Europe (wheat is imported from France, whilst most rye and triticale are sourced from Germany) as the second-largest contributor. Secondly, Indonesia's contribution is amplified (which is in line with the larger contribution of palm kernel expeller). And third, some new countries have also entered the map (Cuba, Guatemala, Paraguay, India, and Pakistan) with small contributions, due to cane molasses replacing beet molasses. Nevertheless, the Netherlands still has a weight share of 7%.

The sensitivity analysis uses the same fodder quantity per FU (0,228 kgs) and the results can be found in table 3. Full tables and maps of alternative results can be found in the complementary data files. The results exhibit lower environmental impacts for nearly all impact indicators under the alternative assumption. Especially ecotoxicity of water, freshwater eutrophication, and land use depict significant reductions. Besides reduced impacts, the proportional distribution of local impacts is also shifted. Most notably, India now bears 25% of the water use impacts, despite their weight contribution of 2%. Indonesia is now the largest contributor (25%) to the total land use impact, mostly due to soybean hulls replacing soybean meal. The extra soybean hulls may have the same weight share, but the economic allocation factor is lower – this dynamic is elaborately explained in section 4.2 – which leads to reduced impacts in Brazil.

Dairy fodder composition in 2019 according to Hospers et al. (2022)

Figure 12: Percentual composition of Dutch dairy fodder in 2019 according to Hospers et al. (2022). The category “other” consists of chalk, citrus pulp, magnesium oxide, palm oil, premix, salt, sunflower meal, triticale, and other minor additions

	EUT-FW [kg P eq.]	EUT-TR [mol N eq.]	LU-S [pt.]	WU [m ³ depr. eq.]	TOX-W [CTUe]	LUC [kg CO ₂ eq.]
Veraart et al. (2023)	6,007E-05	0,003969	22,083	0,06290	33,47	0,07967
Hospers et al. (2022)	4,354E-05	0,003151	16,54	0,06995	16,15	0,05022
Veraart - Hospers	1,652E-05	0,0008180	5,539	-0,007050	17,31	0,02944
Hospers / Veraart	72%	79%	75%	111%	48%	63%

Table 3: Comparison of the total environmental impacts per FU

4.4.4 Combined uncertainty

The combination of the uncertainties of sections 4.4.1 and 4.4.3 gives a range for the total environmental impact per indicator. Table 4 displays a significant uncertainty range around the current total environmental impact. The combined sensitivity analyses show that the environmental impacts may vary between 59% lower and 37% higher than the results presented in this chapter. Note that these uncertainty ranges are not directly applicable to the total impacts per country because they are the sum of each individual (varying) uncertainty per country.

	EUT-FW [kg P eq.]	EUT-TR [mol N eq.]	LU-S [pt.]	WU [m ³ depr. eq.]	TOX-W [CTUe]	LUC [kg CO ₂ eq.]
Lower	62%	68%	64%	95%	41%	54%
upper	123%	123%	123%	137%	123%	123%

Table 4: Combined uncertainty range for the totals per environmental impact indicator

5 Discussion

This study identified the origin of Dutch dairy fodder in 2019. Based on the identified origins, localised environmental impacts were calculated utilizing an LCA-inspired methodology and these have been proportionally divided over the shadow places of Dutch dairy production. This chapter sets out to look at these findings through the theoretical lens of telecoupling as has been described in chapter 2. The sector's claim to use 100% sustainable soy is discussed, followed by recommendations for mitigation and finally a meta-limitation discussion.

5.1 Telecoupled through fodder production

Looking at dairy production through telecoupling displays the Netherlands as the receiving system of fodder. The findings shed light upon the shadow places, revealing the countries that are sending fodder. This research has identified a total of 28 sending systems, which culminate into a broad web of fodder flows. Moreover, the calculation of localised impacts in terms of 6 different indicators displays the environmental interconnectedness of the effects of the telecoupled dairy production system. The results in the preceding chapter show that, except for terrestrial eutrophication, between 42% - 100% of the local environmental effects due to feed are borne by the sending systems, which indicates the magnitude of the telecoupling. All in all, the findings provide a comprehensive answer to the research question: to what extent are Dutch dairy production and its environmental impacts telecoupled through its fodder production?

Now that the research question is answered, it is valuable to zoom out and take a meta-level perspective. The multitude of sending systems, each with affected environments, not only display the scale of the telecoupling but also its complexity. And even though it may look like it due to the nature of the methodology, dairy production is not a static system. Instead, it is an ever-changing web of interdependencies and cause-effect relationships. This study has performed a sensitivity analysis that proves this characteristic.

Besides showing the results' range of uncertainty, the sensitivity analysis illustrates the ease with which the web of production and effects changes. A mere substitution of a couple of ingredients causes the web to shift drastically, which highlights just how dynamic and telecoupled Dutch dairy production is. According to Hospers et al. (2022), the fodder composition changes yearly, following market prices and availability. Consequently, the distribution of localised impacts is constantly being altered.

An example that underlines this nature is the current war in Ukraine. The results show that Ukraine has the highest weight contribution of fodder in 2019. Russia's invasion in early 2022 disrupted the global food (and feed) markets. Luckily for Dutch dairy farmers, this did not cause any direct problems as fodder producers were able to quickly fill the gap left by Ukraine by substituting (imports of) fodder ingredients against an increased price (Jongeneel et al., 2022). However, this in turn led to food insecurity in countries reliant on inexpensive cereal and oilseed imports from Ukraine, such as Egypt, Turkey, and the middle east (Van Meijl et al., 2022). The war in Ukraine is a prime example of how local changes can affect distant local environments through the globalized dynamics of an increasingly telecoupled world.

The case of dairy production is nestled in a broader socio-economic context. The results, as well as the example of the war in Ukraine, demonstrate how the globalized fodder markets, through competition and ease of substitution, generate significant stability for the consumers of fodder in the Netherlands. For Dutch fodder companies, often large agri-business conglomerates, price is the leading determining factor for their fodder composition. Following the argumentation of Plumwood (2008), fodder has environmental effects in places that fodder companies, nor their customers, do not know and do not need to know about in the current commodity regime. In conclusion, the competition in the global fodder market provides both stability and low prices for fodder consumers. And besides the fact that globalization in a sense enabled over-expansion of the Dutch livestock production (which caused the current nitrogen crisis), global fodder markets benefit the Dutch environment by outsourcing the environmental impact associated with fodder production.

On the other side of the story are the fodder-producing countries. It is the same competition that harms places of production in two ways. First, individual farmers are highly replaceable, which brings about great instability. Second, in order to remain competitive in the market, farmers are pressured to intensify and expand, which leads to the environmental effects discussed in this study. And not only do the farmers suffer from e.g. the degradation of their land but also the surrounding (eco-) systems and neighbouring communities, as well as the places downstream of the sending systems. Within the theory of telecoupling, these places are called spillover systems. These effects may create feedback loops within and between sending (and spillover) systems, culminating in an increasingly complex network of systems, causes and effects.

It can be concluded that even local impacts cannot be studied locally, as they are the result of telecoupled cause-effect relationships. This study has shown what the (reach of) effects are of actions in the Netherlands, which at the same time highlights the possibilities of transforming these negative effects into positive impacts. A holistic view is needed to comprehensively understand the dynamics between the distant coupled human-natural systems, and ensure the effects are changed for the better.

5.2 The claim of using 100% responsible soy

Soy is an especially problematic fodder ingredient because it leads to over 84% of the deforestation caused by Dutch dairy fodder. However, according to the Dutch dairy sector, 100% of the soy used for dairy fodder is roundtable responsible soy (RTRS) certified (NZO, 2021). The sector states that it uses 100% sustainable soy and therefore, Dutch dairy production would not cause any deforestation. However, the world wide nature fund (WWF) has debunked this claim and proven that soy used in the Netherlands does in fact cause a devastating amount of deforestation (Jennings et al., 2022). On top of that, the Dutch branch of WWF has stated that they “have lost faith in RTRS as an effective method to stop deforestation” (Rietveld, 2021). Therefore, it can be concluded that the findings in this study on land use change are still valid, despite the sector’s claim to be 100% sustainable.

5.3 Recommendations for impact mitigation

By identifying the shadow places, this study takes the first step in the right direction. As Plumwood (2008) argues, we should care for the shadow places of our consumption as much as we care for our place of dwelling. Identification of these shadow places, as well as the calculation and localisation of environmental impacts, were the first step to achieving this goal. The next step is to mitigate these impacts. In this section, four strategies for mitigation are briefly discussed.

5.3.1 Alternative sourcing or alternative ingredients

From the findings of this study, it is easy to conclude that producing soy in Brazil has higher local impacts compared to producing soy in the United States. For example, Brazilian soy production brings about 2,8x more freshwater eutrophication and 180x more land use change per kg of soy. Hence, it may seem logical to conclude that soy should exclusively be sourced from the United States. An even better alternative would be the complete replacement of soy with a different ingredient, presumably in greater quantities, which boasts a similar protein content. These recommendations may appear straight forward, yet require careful investigation to overcome the two possible complications.

First, while US-soy may be more environmentally friendly in terms of most local indicators, it is 100x worse in terms of water deprivation. This demands trade-offs to be made between impact indicators. In this example, the answer may seem straight forward, but even here it is essential to consider that this study does not take all possible sustainability impact indicators into account (missing e.g. social and economic, as well as global environmental effects). Assuming that the most vital impact indicators are calculated, it is time to balance them against each other. In LCA methodology this is referred to as ‘weighing’ and yields a single score impact value that represents the overall sustainability of a product. It is considered the most controversial step in LCA because the chosen weighing factors significantly influence the outcome of the comparison (Prado et al., 2020). Supposing this is done reasonably and fair, there is still a second complication.

Still, due to the telecoupled nature of fodder production, (abruptly) substituting an exporting country or ingredient can have unwanted cascading or spillover effects. The soy telecoupling literature proves these dynamics, showing how the Sino-Brazilian soy trade has negatively affected the maize food security and prices in Brazil (Silva et al., 2017), as well as having adverse effects on environments in China (among others) in terms of terrestrial nitrogen balance (Sun et al., 2018). In conclusion, as a result of the complex connections between human-environments in the sending, receiving, and spillover systems, rigorous investigation of the complete telecoupled system is crucial to understand its intricate cause-and-effect relationships and assess possible interventions.

5.3.2 True cost accounting

Another approach to care for the shadow places as if they were our own places of dwelling is by putting a price tag on the negative effects. True Cost Accounting (TCA) is a method of accounting that strives to include all social, economic, and environmental externalities of a product (Baker et al., 2020). TCA aims to mitigate these externalities in two ways. First, by both collecting money to directly compensate for environmental impacts or invest in e.g. more sustainable production methods. Second, by creating an economic incentive to encourage more sustainable practices. This is similar to alternative sourcing or alternative ingredients but then operationalised by the market forces instead of concrete policies.

TCA faces similar challenges, such as the problem of weighing. Instead of weighing to achieve a dimensionless single impact indicator, the products should be appropriately priced to encompass both costs and benefits of all externalities. An example of a method that puts a price on sustainability impacts is the eco-costs LCA methodology (Vogtländer, 2016). Yet, concerns on whether accurate monetary valuation is possible and effective, since it is designed more as a tool for design making rather than generating specific sustainable solutions (Baker et al., 2020). Additionally, opponents of TCA argue that it is impossible to guarantee the collected money arrives at and solves the related issues. And similarly to alternative sourcing, TCA could have unwanted effects due to the telecoupled nature of Dutch dairy fodder. Ultimately, more research is essential to better understand these dynamics, and to assess TCA methodologies and their possible effects.

5.3.3 Domestic fodder production

Alternatively, Dutch dairy production could re-integrate fodder production onto its own land. By producing fodder locally, farmers and consumers regain sight of the production of the products they use and consume. It brings the required inputs and environmental impacts back into the light. Following Plumwood (2008), this should create an incentive for both farmers and society as a whole to reduce the environmental burden of fodder production.

The central concern against this strategy is that the Netherlands does not have the space to fulfil the complete dairy fodder demand, nor the right climate, which results in lower yields cascading into even more land and input requirements. The findings show that using biodiversity as an inaccurate correction for the climatic difference, an additional 19% of the Netherlands' surface area must be allocated to domestically feed the Dutch cattle herd. If the cattle herd is fed locally, the other livestock sectors must undoubtedly be locally fed under the same reasoning, which would require 2/3 of the Netherlands' surface area for soy alone (Jennings et al., 2022).

Additionally, making such changes will have both intracoupled (interconnectedness and interdependencies within a system) and telecoupled effects. Dutch land allocation will drastically shift, having unforeseeable effects on human-environment interactions within as well as outside of the Netherlands. Obviously, in relation to the aforementioned circumstances, internalising the current demand for fodder is impossible. However, domestic production could be feasible as complementary to the following mitigation strategy.

5.3.4 Degrowth

Degrowth is defined as the equitable downscaling of production and consumption in order to stay within planetary boundaries. It is a strongly debated topic in academics, and a consensus is yet to be reached (van den Bergh & Kallis, 2012). In the context of dairy, a degrowth approach suggests the downscaling of Dutch production and consumption. In addition to reducing telecoupled environmental impacts, domestic environmental- and animal welfare issues are also decreased. A reduction in milk production would also free more space in the Netherlands to increase local, sustainable fodder production.

Moreover, according to the Dairy sector, the Netherlands export 65% of the dairy it produces (ZuivelNL, 2020). This indicates that Dutch consumption should therefore be unaffected, depending on the rate of degrowth. Nevertheless, similar to the other mitigation strategies, degrowth may result in both wanted and unwanted intra- or telecoupled effects and feedbacks.

5.3.5 General conclusion on recommendations

As the telecoupling literature suggests, nothing happens in a vacuum anymore. Dutch dairy production is incredibly interconnected to places all around the globe. This study has shown the tip of the iceberg by revealing the web of interdependencies and effected environments connected to dairy production through its fodder flows. Therefore, actions in the Netherlands affect distant human-natural systems through complex cause-effect relationships and feedback loops.

It is concluded that, regardless of the mitigation strategy, more research is needed to achieve a rigorous understanding of the telecoupled dynamics of Dutch dairy production. On top of that, a holistic approach is imperative to consider all direct and indirect effects per mitigation strategy. This yields a complete overview of all wanted and unwanted consequences, from which an assessment can be made of each strategy's sustainability trade-offs. Only then the telecoupling of Dutch dairy production can be used to its advantage: maximizing the positive impact the Netherlands could have on human-natural systems all around the world.

5.4 Meta limitation discussion

The previously conducted LCA literature quantifies the impact of milk over its complete life cycle, but the studies are often outdated, only focussing on carbon emissions and never localised. In contrast, telecoupling literature rigorously studies the interconnectedness and interdependencies of distantly coupled production systems, yet only focuses on soy and does not quantify effects. This study fills this gap through the combination of the strengths of both. Here, the quantified and technical approach of LCA is complemented by localisation and placed in the broader context of a telecoupled world to interpret the findings. This methodology yielded a comprehensive overview of the spatial distribution of (the impacts of) fodder production, shedding light upon the shadow places of Dutch dairy production. But despite these strengths, this study also has considerable limitations.

First of all, the approach of this study is very broad. On the positive side, this approach enabled a practical localisation of impacts on a country level. At the same time, the findings are merely averaged impacts per country. For locally characterised impacts, such as water and land use, it may misrepresent the actual water stress caused by crop production. Especially in large countries with varying climates and population densities (e.g. the United States or Ukraine), these impact categories hold a higher uncertainty. This, however, does not mean that the findings are unreliable. The results still indicate to what extent distant environments are affected and give valuable insights into the interconnectedness and distribution of these impacts.

Second, the approach is only a delayed snapshot of reality. As has been previously discussed, a change in fodder composition has significant impacts on the distribution and magnitude of interdependencies and impacts. Similarly, fodder quantities change every year (in an upwards trend) (van der Meulen, 2022) and changes in e.g. nitrogen legislation or milk quotas would reduce the value of this study's findings as a depiction of reality. At the same time, the volatility proven in this study can also be positively interpreted. It highlights the reach Dutch actions could have to positively change human-natural systems all over the world, given that the actions are well-considered.

Furthermore, the reference year for nearly all data in this study is 2019 (some exceptions regarding the LCA impact database, where some data may be as old as 2010). On top of this, better (or worse) farming practices may change the extent to which local environments are impacted. Hence, the findings are not a depiction of what is happening *right now*, nor an averaged picture of what has happened over e.g. the past 10 years.

Third, sustainability consists of three elements: environment, society, and economy. These three are interdependent, meaning that social sustainability influences both environmental and economic sustainability and vice versa. To keep the research boundaries manageable, this study analysed only environmental sustainability, as if it existed in a vacuum. However, it is imperative to holistically investigate all three elements of sustainability to robustly understand the telecoupled dairy production system. Although such research may be harder to quantify (due to the qualitative nature of social sustainability), it still yields relevant insights, especially for the assessment of mitigation strategies.

In sum, the web of fodder flows and their impacts are extremely versatile. Once again, this does not negate the value of the findings but underscores the need for their interpretation as an indication of reality in the right order of magnitude. This study aims to illuminate the shadow places, display the complex relationships between distant human-natural systems and estimate the extent to which distant environments are impacted. Given these objectives, the adopted approach is deemed appropriate. However, if the goal is to precisely study how local environments and communities are affected by fodder production, a deeper empirical methodology is advised. And if the research objective is to thoroughly understand how the distant systems interact and have interacted over time, a broader temporal scale is recommended.

6 Conclusion

The shadow places of production support our lives and grow us similarly to our special, recognized place of dwelling. We have to acknowledge all these shadow places, the places of fodder production, too as our place and care for them similarly as we care for our place of dwelling. This study has taken the first step in this process. By identifying these places, and quantifying and localising the environmental impacts related to dairy production, these shadow places are brought into the light.

This study has identified a total of 28 countries as the shadow places of production, defining them as sending systems. Through the use of an LCA-inspired methodology, the environmental effects of dairy fodder production were quantified in terms of 6 impact indicators. Going beyond regular LCA, this study has localised these impacts, revealing that on average 60% of the environmental impacts of feed are borne by the shadow places. Mapping the results visualised how fodder production and its impacts are divided over the shadow places, showing that Brazil and Ukraine suffer the most environmental impacts. On top of that, the sensitivity analysis revealed how variable these results are and highlights the ease with which the magnitude and distribution of environmental impacts change.

Applying the theoretical lens of telecoupling revealed how Dutch dairy production is not simply 'Dutch', but that it consists of an ever-changing web of distant, yet interconnected and interdependent places of production. This study shows that local effects are the result of a broad network of telecoupled cause-effect relationships, which cannot be studied in isolation. It is shown how actions in the Netherlands have far-reaching, negative effects on distant human-natural systems. Whilst at the same time highlighting the opportunities for Dutch actions to reduce environmental damage all over the globe.

Because now that it is known to what extent Dutch dairy farming and its environmental impacts are telecoupled through fodder flow, it is time to take the second step: mitigation. Several strategies were discussed, but it is concluded that it is crucial to further understand the complex interrelationships and telecoupled dynamics of the dairy production system.

In order to achieve such rigorous understanding, this study recommends several topics for future research. This research purposefully took a snapshot view of the case, but a wider temporal scale could yield significant insights into the dynamics within the system. Besides, for a comprehensive understanding, it is imperative to analyse the social and economic sustainability of the telecoupling. After this research is conducted, it is possible to make sure all (un-)wanted effects per mitigation strategy are considered and holistically assessed. Because now that the telecoupled environmental effects of dairy fodder production are quantified and localized, the goal is to entirely reduce these effects. Rather than relocate them again to new shadow places.

7 Bibliography

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Appendix A

Ingredient	Calculation	Assumptions
Beet molasses	Market mix	According to the Eurostat data, the Net import for beet molasses that the Netherlands has with the world is negative, meaning that it is an exporting country in beet molasses, and all beet molasses used in the Netherlands are produced domestically. This varies from the results in the report by Veraart et al. (2023), which states that 30% of beet molasses are imported, yet does not specify from where further than “outside of Europe”. Since this paper uses the same methodology and data as described in Veraart et al. (2023), the differences in data are unexplained. Therefore it is assumed that 100% of beet molasses used in dairy fodder is produced in the Netherlands.
Beet vinasse	Market mix and impact	There is no specific data on vinasse. Since vinasse is the rest-product of ethanol production from molasses, the same market mix and impact data as beet molasses is assumed.
Maize DDGS	Market mix	No specific trade data can be found for Maize DDGS (dried distiller grain soluble). Since it is a processed maize product, the same market mix as maize is assumed.
Maize DDGS	Impact	No specific impact data can be found for maize DDGS, so the impact data for maize DDG is taken. For most countries, maize DDG impact data is also not available. Here the country-specific data of maize is taken * 0,73. This is the average factor between the impacts of maize and maize DDG for other countries in the database.
Wheat gluten feed and wheat grits	Market mix	No specific trade data can be found for wheat gluten feed or grits. Since they mainly consist of wheat, the same market mix as wheat is assumed
Citrus pulp	Market mix	There is no market mix data available for citrus pulp directly. Since the majority of citrus pulp is made from oranges, the market mix for oranges is assumed.
Rapeseed meal	Impact	For most countries, there is no exact impact data on the production of rapeseed meal. Here the country-specific data of dried rapeseed is taken * 0,42. This is the average factor between the impacts of rapeseed and rapeseed meal for other countries in the database.
Soybean hulls and soybean meal	Impacts	For some countries, there is no exact impact data on the production of soybean hulls. Here the country-specific data of soybeans * 0,43 is taken. This is the average factor between the impacts of soybean and soybean hulls for other countries in the database. For soybean meal this factor is 0,86
Sunflower oilcake	Impacts	There is no available impact data for sunflower oilcake (or any other sunflower products) available for Latvia. Hence the data for Estonia is taken.
Citrus pulp	Impact	There is no country-specific impact data available for citrus pulp, only a global average. This global average is taken for every country.
Palm kernel expeller	Market mix	Germany, Romania, and Slovenia have a cumulative market share of 16,4% according to the trade balance. However, since palm oil is not farmed in these countries, it is assumed that these were grown in Indonesia (which is by far the largest producer in the World).
Cane molasses	Market mix	A significant part of the market share consists of countries that do not grow cane sugar. Therefore it is assumed that these are exports from India (the country with the largest market share) and traded through the European countries in question to the Netherlands.
All	Impact	For the minority countries (share <1%) that are grouped under “other countries”, the non-localised impact is calculated by using the impact values of the country that has the largest share for that ingredient.

Table 5: Ingredient-specific assumptions to fill the data gaps

Appendix B

Barley		Beet molasses/vinasse		Maize (DDGS)	
NL – Netherlands	10,73%	NL – Netherlands	100%	NL – Netherlands	2,12%
BE - Belgium	7,85%			BR - Brazil	5,45%
DE - Germany	24,85%			FR - France	12,49%
FR - France	37,68%			LT - Lithuania	1,86%
GB - United Kingdom	14,06%			RO - Romania	8,12%
LV - Latvia	1,38%			UA - Ukraine	68,50%
SE - Sweden	1,56%			Other countries	1,45%
Other countries	1,89%				
Rapeseed meal		Rye		Soybean hulls/meal	
AU - Australia	11,72%	NL - Netherlands	9,68%	BR - Brazil	45,41%
BE - Belgium	10,81%	DE - Germany	78,96%	CA - Canada	8,98%
BG - Bulgaria	8,86%	DK - Denmark	2,11%	US - United States	39,05%
LT - Lithuania	1,93%	FR - France	5,10%	UY - Uruguay	5,48%
LV - Latvia	1,87%	PL - Poland	4,01%	Other countries	1,08%
RO - Romania	5,50%	Other countries	0,14%		
UA - Ukraine	57,76%				
Other countries	1,55%				
Sunflower meal		Triticale		Cane molasses	
AR - Argentina	36,71%	NL - Netherlands	9,32%	CU - Cuba	1,88%
BG - Bulgaria	13,30%	BE - Belgium	2,64%	GT - Guatemala	13,15%
EE - Estonia	1,26%	DE - Germany	64,13%	IN - India	80,46%
LV - Latvia	4,93%	FR - France	19,53%	PK - Pakistan	2,82%
UA - Ukraine	43,76%	LT - Lithuania	1,28%	PY - Paraguay	1,70%
Other countries	0,04%	LU - Luxembourg	2,21%		
		Other countries	0,89%		
Wheat (grits)		Citrus pulp		Palm Kernel	
NL - Netherlands	18,41%	AR - Argentina	1,29%	ID - Indonesia	96,33%
BE - Belgium	6,50%	EG - Egypt	23,39%	MY - Malaysia	3,67%
BG - Bulgaria	2,62%	ES - Spain	10,83%	Other countries	0,00%
DE - Germany	15,05%	MA - Morocco	9,85%		
DK - Denmark	1,24%	PE - Peru	1,61%		
FR - France	45,15%	UY - Uruguay	2,17%		
GB - United Kingdom	3,54%	ZA - South Africa	45,63%		
RO - Romania	1,39%	ZW - Zimbabwe	5,24%		
SE - Sweden	1,20%				
UA - Ukraine	2,61%				
Other countries	2,29%				

Table 6: Market mix per fodder ingredient

Appendix C

Ingredient	Type	QTY [kg]	EUT-FW [kg P eq.]	EUT-TR [mol N eq.]	WU [m3 deprived Eq.]	TOX-W [CTUe]	LUC [Kg CO2 eq.]	LU-S [pt.]	
Barley	Absolute	0,003442	1,14E-06	0,000119	7,45E-05	0,366045	5,66E-05	0,357218	
	%	1,51%	1,90%	3,01%	0,12%	1,09%	0,07%	1,62%	
Beet molasses	Absolute	0,005642	8,14E-07	5,62E-05	2,58E-05	0,063239	1,17E-07	0,063098	
	%	2,47%	1,35%	1,42%	0,04%	0,19%	0,00%	0,29%	
Maize	Absolute	0,034606	6,2E-06	0,000536	0,029596	4,871906	0,00277	2,45785	
	%	15,18%	10,32%	13,51%	47,05%	14,56%	3,48%	11,13%	
Maize DDGS	Absolute	0,005037	6,59E-07	5,7E-05	0,003144	0,517551	0,000294	0,261096	
	%	2,21%	1,10%	1,44%	5,00%	1,55%	0,37%	1,18%	
Palm kernel expeller	Absolute	0,027359	4,61E-06	0,000261	0,000578	0,141427	0,005746	2,961755	
	%	12,00%	7,68%	6,58%	0,92%	0,42%	7,21%	13,41%	
Rapeseed meal	Absolute	0,021995	3,28E-06	0,000277	0,00036	3,960732	0,002291	1,423703	
	%	9,65%	5,45%	6,99%	0,57%	11,83%	2,88%	6,45%	
Rye	Absolute	0,016203	6,78E-06	0,000811	0,000303	6,273972	2,08E-06	1,954575	
	%	7,11%	11,29%	20,43%	0,48%	18,75%	0,00%	8,85%	
Soybean hulls	Absolute	0,025446	6,48E-06	0,000182	0,005698	1,937602	0,016477	1,981218	
	%	11,16%	10,78%	4,60%	9,06%	5,79%	20,68%	8,97%	
Soybean meal	Absolute	0,02522	1,97E-05	0,000561	0,017981	6,024294	0,050834	6,156361	
	%	11,06%	32,84%	14,15%	28,59%	18,00%	63,81%	27,88%	
Sunflower meal	Absolute	0,014618	2,68E-06	0,000195	0,002365	3,264178	0,000792	2,147583	
	%	6,41%	4,46%	4,92%	3,76%	9,75%	0,99%	9,73%	
Triticale	Absolute	0,020111	6,81E-06	0,000833	0,001123	5,949718	0,000408	2,229333	
	%	8,82%	11,33%	20,99%	1,78%	17,78%	0,51%	10,10%	
Beet vinasse	Absolute	0,005757	8,3E-07	5,74E-05	2,64E-05	0,064531	1,19E-07	0,064388	
	%	2,53%	1,38%	1,45%	0,04%	0,19%	0,00%	0,29%	
Citruspulp	Absolute	0,011731	6,44E-08	2,12E-05	0,001623	0,031931	-3,1E-06	0,02447	
	%	5,15%	0,11%	0,53%	2,58%	0,10%	0,00%	0,11%	
Other	Absolute	0,010822	No impacts, only for weight						
	%	4,75%							
Total	Absolute	0,227989	6,01E-05	0,003969	0,062897	33,46712	0,079667	22,08265	

Table 7: Complementary table to figure 4, including absolute totals per impact indicator, per FU. QTY = kgs of fodder per functional unit, EUT-FW = freshwater eutrophication, EUT-TR = terrestrial eutrophication, WU = localised water use in terms of m³ deprived, TOX-W = freshwater ecotoxicity, LUC = land use change, LU-S = land use based on soil quality